

THE IMPACT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE MODELS ON THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE ORGANIZATION

Tamar Gambashidze,

Doctor of Economics (Ph. D.),

Associate Professor at Georgian Technical University

Maia Chechelashvili

Doctor of Economics (Ph. D.),

Associate Professor at Georgian Technical University

Abstract

In today's increasingly competitive conditions, reaching the desired organizational efficiency level attracts both academicians' and practitioners' interest much more. The factors influencing organizational efficiency are examined with highly increasing importance. Considering organizational culture as one of the factors, the effect of the types of organizational culture on organizational efficiency is questioned. The determining effect of the organizational environment getting complex on the strategy that enables achieving organizational level can play a significant role in the relationship between organizational culture and organizational efficiency. The individual effect of the organizational leaders on the efficiency strategies is viewed in terms of their values. In this study, the relationship between organizational culture and organizational efficiency and the effect of stability or variability of internal and external environment on this relation is investigated. Besides, the values of self-direction, stimulation, and power that leaders have are researched. 40 top managers/organizational founders are selected for sampling in the health sector. The questionnaire method is utilized for gathering data. The findings show that organizational culture types are related to some organizational efficiency dimensions. The stability or variability of the internal and external organizational environment and the top manager's values (self-direction and stimulation) play a moderator role in this relationship.

Keywords: Loyalty to the organization; justification of own behavior, individual and collective culture, perception of the organizational environment, social control system.

Organizational culture has always been an integral part of people's creative work, which is becoming increasingly important in the context of globalization. Today, it is one of the most important factors in the success of the organization. The higher the organizational culture, the more stable and efficient the work of any work team.

Transnational corporations are a key element in the global economic globalization process. Through the implementation of global strategies, they play a leading role in developing global economic ties that unite regional and global markets. The share of transnational companies in the Georgian market and economy is quite large, they have a well-organized and flexible management, which helps them to manage effectively. In the context of a weak Georgian economy, large transnational corporations need to enter to increase economic parameters. The structure and types of transnational companies, and development phases are described—principles and importance of organizational structure design in transnational companies. The paper discusses the role of transnational companies in the globalization of the world economy and their impact on transition economies. Based on the analysis of the respondents' survey, a conclusion has been made about the role of transnational companies in developing the Georgian economy. Conclusions are made at the end of the paper.

Organizational culture influences and manages the behavior of team members in transnational organizations, but its definition is quite complex and there is no general agreement on what exactly corporate culture means. Organizational culture arises when employees

share knowledge and assumptions and find a way to internal integration. National culture has a significant impact on organizational culture, therefore it is important to study both corporate culture and culture in general.

Culture plays a crucial role in the formation of an internal organization of a company. It creates a kind of social control system that determines what is "right" or "wrong" for an employee. That is, it determines how an employee should behave within a particular company. It helps the individual to develop within themselves a perception, behavior, and skills appropriate to the company's values and goals.

Therefore, organizational culture creates a context for the employed individual and allows him to adapt to the environment. The culture of the organization must be in harmony with the structure and strategy of the company. It is the force that drives the effective work of the organization.

Organizational culture is not an entity in itself in transnational organizations but is a concept formed as a result of the influence of the cultural narrative in society. The reason for this is that the company is made up of people who are part of this community. That is, they combine values, skills, and skills outside the organization. Consequently, the company depends entirely on the culture of the society and its characteristics.

In Georgia's weak economy, large transnational companies need to increase their economic parameters.

Ultimately, the center of organizational culture values is not the individual but the company itself and its goals. Accordingly, it is considered a measure of the success of the organization. There are many approaches to determining the impact of culture on an organization.

Model V. State explores the impact of culture on organizational life through seven processes:

- cooperation between individuals and constituent parts of the organization;
- making decisions;
- control;
- communications;
- loyalty to the organization;
- perception of the organizational environment;
- justification of own behavior.

The first three processes are related to the first, superficial level of organizational culture or patterns of organizational behavior, and the next four - to the second, lower level, which has a "value" basis. The effectiveness of the organization's functioning depends on how these processes are carried out. In some organizations, teamwork is the highest value, in others - internal competition. In other words, everything depends on which philosophy prevails: individualistic or collectivist. Let's consider several models of the influence of culture on the competitiveness of the organization

Peters-Waterman model. The authors of the well-known bestseller "In Search of Successful Management" vol. Peters and R. Waterman discovered a connection between culture and organizational success. Peters and Waterman argue that successful organizations have three sets of values:

1. Successful companies strive to realize their values in what Peters and Waterman call the "action bias." Such companies emphasize the value of autonomy and initiative and encourage employees to take reasonable risks, such as finding new ways to deliver high-quality products or services to customers.

2. The second set is determined by the nature of the organization's mission, that is, what the organization does and how it tries to do it. Peters and Waterman argue that managers must first establish values that focus on what the organization does best and maintain control over core activities. It also involves building close relationships with customers and adopting customer-centric norms to improve the company's competitive position.

3. The third set of values is related to the organization's operations. A company should try to establish values and norms that encourage its employees to perform at the highest possible level. These values are shaped by the belief that production is driven by employees and that respect for the individual is the primary means by which a company can create the culture necessary for productive operation.

Parsons model (Talcott Parsons). In a more general way, the connection between the culture and the results of the organization's work is discussed by the American sociologist T. It is presented in the Parsons

model. The model is developed based on the characteristics of certain functions that any social system, including an organization, must perform to survive and succeed. The abbreviation of the English names of these functions gave this model its name **AGIL**:

- adaptation;
- goals; achieving
- integration;
- Legitimacy.

Queen-Rohrbach (R. Queen, J. Rohrbach) model. Persson's ideas were spread and concretized by R. Quinn and J. Rohrbach in their model "Competing Values and Organizational Effectiveness", which explains the influence of certain groups of values on the effectiveness of the organization. In the development of the AGIL model, this influence was proposed for consideration in not one but three dimensions. Therefore, the so-called "competing values" model was used.

This model includes three dimensions:

1. Integration - differentiation:
2. Internal focus - external focus:
3. Means/tools - results/indicators:

This model describes the values of the organization's culture about each approach to determining effectiveness and compares the perspective of one approach to all other approaches.

d. Denison's model of organizational culture considers four dimensions of organizational culture assessment: external focus, internal focus, stability, and flexibility. The combination of these characteristics gives the parameters of culture assessment: involvement, stability, adaptability, and mission.

References

1. Organisational Culture, (2003) ICFAI Centre for Management Research, ECCH Collection, <http://www.ecch.cranfield.ac.uk>. 3M's Annual Report (2006) 'Working Our Magic', USA:3M,
2. Gambashidze Tamar et al. Contemporary Business Challenges in a Globalized World: Research, Study, Examination (Volume 3) // Economic transformation of the pandemic in Georgia Collective monograph. Saarbrücken, Saarland, Germany. (2022).
3. http://solutions.3m.com/wps/portal/3M/en_US/our/company/information/ 3M McKnight Principles, 3M Leadership, History, CEO and Corporate Officers.
4. http://solutions.3m.com/wps/portal/3m/en_US/our/company/information/history/
5. Yasas Pathiranage-Organizational Culture and Business Performance: An Empirical Study-University of Kelaniya,2019
6. Robertson, International Review of Industrial and Organizational Psychology, Wiley, Chichester Schein, E H (2014)